

The cyanate complex of copper(II) shows bands at 2135 cm^{-1} and 1338 cm^{-1} , assignable to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ vibrations. It has been demonstrated⁸ that for N-bonded NCO group, the $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ appears at 1300 cm^{-1} and for O-bonded NCO group it occurs at a much lower frequency (below 1200 cm^{-1}). It is therefore concluded that in the present copper(II) chelate the NCO group is N-bonded to the metal ion as $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ appears to absorb at 1338 cm^{-1} . The electronic spectra (nujol mull) (Table) of thiocyanato and cyanato complexes of copper(II) shows band $\sim 17,000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ —indicating the presence of highly distorted octahedral ligand arrangement around copper(II) ion.

The i.r. spectral data of nickel(II) complexes (Table) suggest S-bonded SCN and N-bonded NCO ligand to be present in (III) and (IV) respectively. The magnetic moment values (see experimental) and the electronic absorption spectral data (Table) suggest distorted octahedral geometry for the chelates.

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New Compounds of Chromium(V) : Tetraphenylarsonium and Tetraphenylphosphonium Oxotetrachloro-Chromate(V)

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CHROMIUM(V) is well known in the form of oxotetra- and penta chloro-chromate(V) discovered by Weinland and coworkers¹ to which important

additions were made by others². All of them, as are known, are sensitive to moisture, mildheat, light and storage.

Here we report the preparations and properties of two new compounds in the series which unlike those known, are stable and are obtained from chromyl chloride.

Oxotetrachloro chromate(V) salts of tetraphenylarsonium(I) and tetraphenylphosphonium(II) cations, $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{As}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$ and $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{P}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$ were isolated by reducing chromyl chloride taken in pure acetic acid by dry HCl gas at 0° in the dark condition and precipitating the compounds(I) and (II) with tetraphenylarsonium chloride and tetraphenylphosphonium chloride dissolved in pure acetic acid respectively. The precipitates were filtered in sintered glass gooch crucibles, washed with acetic acid and finally with benzene and dried over concentrated sulphuric acid.

Yields were nearly quantitative. Analytical results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1				
	Cr	Cl	A	O.S.
Found % for (I)	8.80	25.24	10.98	5.06
Calc. % for (I)	8.77	23.94	12.65	5.00
Found % for (II)	9.73	25.23	4.94	4.87
Calc. % for (II)	9.47	25.86	5.64	5.00

A = As in (I) and P in (II), O.S. = Oxidation State.

These compounds are light buff in color and similar in properties and resemble in formula and other properties those in the series having large heterocyclic nitrogen bases acting as cations.

The compound(I) begins to incinerate at 193° and melts at 200° and (II) does the same things at 205° and 228° respectively.

(I) is soluble in methanol, ethanol, acetone, nitrobenzene, nitromethane, dimethylformamide, but insoluble in water, acetic acid, benzene, carbontetrachloride. (II) has similar solubility, but apparently slightly more than (I).

Λ_0 in nitromethane at 22° is 87.68 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2/\text{mole}$ for (I) and 87.14 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2/\text{mole}$ for (II) indicating them to be 1 : 1 electrolytes.³

The magnetic susceptibility was measured at 23° and the corrected magnetic moments were found to be 1.65 B.M. for (I) and 1.72 B.M. for (II) indicating that these contained d^1 systems which substantiate the chemical evidence.

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The IR spectra has been recorded in KBr disc and the peaks (in cm^{-1}) are given below :

(I) 610(v,w); 684(s,sp); 740(s,sp); 900(v,w); 916(w,sp); 948(s,sp); 992(s,sp); 1018(s,sp); 1080(s,sp); 1160(m,sp); 1180(m,sp); 1305(m,sp); 1330(m,sp); 1390(v,w); 1430(s,sp); 1480(s,sp); 1810(v,w); 2250(v,w,B).

(II) 616(v,w); 685(s,sp); 722(s,sp); 755(s,sp); 900(v,w); 925(m,sp); 950(s,sp); 995(s,sp); 1018(s,sp); 1028(m,sp); 1105(s,sh); 1158(m,sp); 1180(m,sp); 1310(m,sp); 1335(m,sp); 1390(v,w); 1432(s,sh); 1480(s,sp); 1587(m,sp); 1612(w,B); 1820(w); 1900(v,w); 2265(w,B).

They indicate the absence of H_2O and HCl . The two spectra show much similarities. The number of peaks in (II) is somewhat more numerous than that in (I). Moreover, the peak at 740 in (I) appears to have split up into two at 722 and 755, both strong and sharp, and new peak are found at 1587 (m,sp) and also at 1900. In (II) some peaks are also shifted to higher wave numbers. In (I) the peaks at 948 and 916 are possibly due to Cr-O group and in (II) those at 950 and 925 indicate Cr-O group.⁴

The electronic spectra has been recorded at 22° in a Beckmann DU2 spectrophotometer in the solid state in nujol mull and also in acetone solution and are presented in Fig. 1.

The peaks (in nm) and the corresponding molar extinction co-efficient (ϵ_M) given in parenthesis, are as follows :

Compound (I) : λ_{max} 440 (198.7); 600 (123.5).

Compound (II) : λ_{max} 400 (275.8); 440 (265.6); 590 (119.4).

Compound (I) in nujol mull : $\lambda_{max} = 440, 460, 560$.

Compound (II) in nujol mull : $\lambda_{max} = 430, 450, 560$.

Fig. 1 Electronic spectra of $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{As}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$ (I) and $(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_4\text{P}[\text{CrOCl}_4]$ (II)

- (I) — Compound(I) in acetone $16 \times 10^{-4} M$ /litre.
 (I) - - - Compound(I) in Nujol(mull) [O.D/4].
 (II) — Compound(II) in acetone $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ /litre.
 (II) - - - Compound(II) in Nujol(mull) [O.D/4].

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